

VOLUME COMPOSITION AND ITS CATEGORIES.

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Abstract. This article discusses the fact that the composition is created using certain tools. Harmonious, proportional and correctly chosen use of instruments testifies to the creative approach to composition.

Keywords: Works of art, volume, composition, symmetrical, asymmetrical, education, volume-spatial, frontal, size.

The laws that are the basis for the creation of works of art are called the laws of harmony. They include the law of balance, the law of unity and subordination. But according to the laws of harmony, one cannot create a composition without auxiliary artistic means. These include, as you know, rhythm, contrast, nuance, similarity, as well as proportion and scale. These are the main means of harmonization. There is no composition without their participation.

Tectonics (category of composition) is a visible reflection of its construction and its raw material essence in the form of an object. It is in tectonics that the relationship between the form and the essence of the product is reflected. Volumetric-spatial structure is the second important category of composition. With it, the shape of the product and the spatial relationship and interaction are determined. A designer cannot create an aesthetically perfect product without considering the space.

It is possible to include works of art that have three dimensions (length, width and height), that is, parameters characterizing the volume and solving artistic tasks, in the volumetric composition. This is sculpture, small plastic, small architectural forms, works of a practical-decorative character, various practical forms, dishes,

furniture, vehicles, clothes, in general, everything that includes design. Even in this simple enumeration, one can feel how widely volumetric composition can be used to create objects that perform tasks in our life and provide human life. Therefore, it can be assumed that it was the volume that first attracted human attention as an object of decoration.

The search for a convenient form is coordinated with the search for ways to give it expressiveness and beauty. Working on a volumetric form, the artist also did not forget about color and texture as active visual tools that help to create one or another artistic image. Even after hundreds of years, the masterpieces of volumetric composition that have reached us amaze with the careful design of everyday objects and the artistic perfection of form, expressiveness of color and texture. There is another aspect that plays an important role in determining the advantages of volumetric composition. This is the problem of adding volume to the surrounding space. Volume has weight, meaning, idea. It is more realistic and noticeable than the frontal composition. It can be placed, hung or placed. Therefore, let's say, the collision of volume and plane should be clearly thought out by the author in order to find the optimal solution. If the work of painting is separated from the environment mainly by means of a frame, which limits the influence of the environment, in this case, the dimensional composition requires a different attitude, a different approach to itself, consisting of co-existence with the environment. is enough. There is another aspect that plays an important role in determining the advantages of volumetric composition. This is the problem of adding volume to the surrounding space. Volume has weight, meaning, idea. It is more realistic and noticeable than the frontal composition. It can be placed, hung or placed.

The composition consists of specific laws and tools. Its basic laws include balance and generality. Balance is manifested differently in symmetrical and asymmetrical compositions. The balance is achieved by the harmony of the amount of elements, their shape, their interaction with the environment, color, textural solution. Compositional tools include descriptive compositional technique,

proportion and scale, contrast and nuance, metrical repetition and rhythm, color, shading, and plasticity.

The deterministic compositional method is an important organizational basis for working on the product form and determines the direction of creative research.

The methodological goal is to master the principles of compositional organization of a three-dimensional object and to obtain composite, composite or composite composite forms that are repeated over and over again for different forms and allow to change options from the same parts. to have practical skills.

Educational tasks:

- finding a composite idea using combinatory formation;
- determination of the nomenclature of type elements;
- combining sizes;
- creating an abstract geometric figure or a spatially recognizable form from the elements of the obtained type.

In addition, color combinations can be used for artistic expressiveness. Three-dimensional composition means that it is perceived from all sides, therefore, the form that appears in the modeling should be critically evaluated from different angles. The basis of the composition can be one of the principles of combinatorics - the folding form (picture - 1).

Compositions can be built into a limited number of types of elements with different standard sizes (picture 2-6).

1 - picture. The principle of folding form in composition.

2 - picture. The composition includes four types of elements with different standard sizes.

3 - picture. The image of an elephant is created due to the same type of element of different sizes.

4 - picture. The composition is based on one type of element of the same size.

5 - picture. The composition consists of two types of elements, one of which has different standard sizes.

6 - picture. The use of volumetric and linear elements that enhance the contrast of forms.

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